

Policy Perspectives on Challenges, Barriers and Potential Enablers of Large-Scale AI-Driven Solutions in Cardiology

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Abstract - The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in cardiology offers substantial opportunities for optimising clinical care, but also brings regulatory, ethical, and technical challenges. This study explores policymakers' and stakeholders' perspectives on the barriers and enablers of large-scale AI implementation in cardiovascular healthcare. A transnational survey was conducted among policymakers, regulators, and healthcare stakeholders across 11 European Union countries, Turkey, and Peru. The findings indicate a consensus that, although current AI regulations offer a basic foundation, healthcare policies are still insufficient for effective AI integration. Key concerns include data privacy, algorithm transparency, liability, and the evolving nature of AI, which hinder long-term regulatory compliance. Respondents emphasised the importance of improving AI literacy, strengthening cybersecurity, and ensuring interoperability within healthcare systems. Despite these challenges, AI is recognised for its potential to enhance diagnostics, personalise care, and optimise healthcare resources. Collaboration among stakeholders, adaptive regulatory frameworks, and innovative evaluation approaches are essential to foster trust and sustainable implementation. The insights from this work may be extended beyond cardiology, offering valuable guidance for AI adoption across various healthcare domains.

Keywords - artificial intelligence, policy making, stakeholder engagement

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly recognised as a transformative force in cardiology, offering advancements in early disease detection, risk stratification, and treatment optimisation to improve patient outcomes [1]. AI-driven tools can enhance diagnostic accuracy, automate clinical workflows, and personalise treatment plans, contributing to more efficient and equitable cardiovascular care [2]. However, despite the promising applications, the large-scale integration of AI into clinical practice remains a complex challenge [3].

Regulatory uncertainties, ethical concerns, and healthcare system readiness represent major barriers to AI implementation [4], [5], [6]. Addressing these challenges requires a structured, multi-stakeholder approach that considers not only regulatory and technical factors, but also economic, organisational, and contextual dynamics [7].

The successful implementation of novel technologies in healthcare, such as those proposed in the European Union (EU) Horizon AI4HF project to improve heart failure treatment, requires innovation in social relations, power dynamics, and governance transformations, falling into the land of social innovation approaches. AI4HF – Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for Personalised Risk Assessment – is a 4-year project (2023-2027) that is co-designing, developing and evaluating a trustworthy AI tool for personalising the care and management of patients with heart failure in co-creation with all relevant stakeholders, with 16 partners from Europe, Peru, and Tanzania [8].

Social innovation is defined by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development as “*the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product, or organisational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities*” [9]. In other words, social innovation refers to innovation in social relations, power dynamics, and governance transformations.

In the healthcare context, social innovation allows for the development and implementation of novel solutions to address complex health challenges, such as the personalized treatment of heart failure. AI-driven tools, such as those being developed in the AI4HF project, rely on innovative thinking to gain acceptance among healthcare providers and patients. The successful implementation of health products and services depends not only on the acceptance among healthcare professionals and patients but also requires the collaboration of stakeholders from different sectors, namely academia, industry, government and civil society, as suggested by the widely adopted Quadruple Helix framework of innovation [10]. Social innovation approaches put the focus on the citizen, or in this case, the patient, being the ones to evolve “*initiatives from a localised level to a macro-level*” [11].

The first step of the social innovation framework applied in the AI4HF project was a thorough stakeholder analysis, to identify the actors who should be engaged in the different phases of the project. To succeed, it is essential that all relevant stakeholders are engaged throughout the design, development, and implementation phases, with a focus on the active role of the patients. Representatives from the five clinical sites of the project located in Czechia, the Netherlands, Peru, Spain, and Tanzania were asked to identify

stakeholders of relevance, as well as their expected role at the different phases of the project, such as *listeners*, *co-thinkers*, or *decision-makers*. Seven key stakeholder groups of relevance were identified: Healthcare Professionals, Patients & Caregivers, Hospital Administration, Ethicists & Regulators, Policy Makers & Health Authorities, AI Developers & Industry, and Payors.

Requirements were gathered through 1. three rounds of international multi-stakeholder social innovation sessions, 2. local working groups at each clinical site to analyse context-specific preferences, barriers, and enablers, and 3. desk research focused on key ethical, legal, and social implications of the implementation of AI in healthcare, such as key ethical principles in AI-driven tools in the context of heart failure treatment; patient reidentification risks; and issues of accountability of AI-driven solutions [12], [13]. Moreover, healthcare and regulatory requirements were gathered through interviews with health technology assessment experts and a review of relevant regulations within the context of AI-driven tools in healthcare.

This study further complements the described work by bringing a specific and usually unexplored perspective, the one of policymakers, regulators, and other healthcare stakeholders, regarding the current state of AI in cardiology, addressing regulatory, economic, organisational, and contextual considerations.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE CONTRIBUTION

A survey was developed to explore the perspectives of policy makers, regulators, public authorities and related stakeholders on the state of play, challenges, barriers and potential enablers and facilitators of large-scale implementation of AI-tools in cardiology. The survey comprised 36 questions, starting with 24 multiple choice items (using Likert scales or single/multiple response options), followed by 12 open-ended questions designed to elicit more in-depth qualitative insights.

The survey was distributed via email to direct contacts of consortium partners and European networks between November 2024 and January 2025. This approach leveraged existing professional connections to reach relevant stakeholders efficiently. A purposive sampling strategy was chosen as participants were selected through established networks and umbrella organisations, which ensured engagement from individuals with relevant expertise or interest in the topic. While this method may limit generalisability, it facilitated targeted responses from key actors within the field.

Descriptive statistical analyses were conducted for the multiple-choice responses, including frequency distributions and percentages. For Likert scale items, response patterns were summarised to capture trends in stakeholder agreement and prioritisation. These analyses provided an overview of perspectives across groups and supported the identification of common priorities and divergences. A rapid thematic analysis was conducted to identify recurring patterns within the qualitative survey responses. Data were reviewed manually to extract common themes, which were then grouped into broader categories based on semantic similarity. This approach enabled timely interpretation of the open-text data while ensuring analytical rigour.

III. RESULTS

Twenty-four valid replies were collected, with respondents from 11 EU-27 countries, plus Turkey and Peru, with no significant oversampling from any country (1-3 representatives per country). The highest participation came from Belgium (N=3), Germany (N=3), Italy (N=3), and Spain (N=3). Other represented countries included the Czech Republic (N=2), Peru (N=2), Portugal (N=2), Denmark (N=1), Estonia (N=1), Ireland (N=1), Latvia (N=1), the Netherlands (N=1), and Turkey (N=1). Two respondents did not respond to some of the optional questions. These partial responses were retained in the analysis, with adjusted sample sizes applied where necessary. Consequently, the total number of responses varies across some items and does not always sum up to twenty-four.

The responses gathered a diverse group of professionals involved in healthcare policy and regulation, from a range of age groups, with the largest representation in the 40-49 age group (9 participants), followed by 30-39 (6 participants), 50-59 (5 participants), and 60+ (4 participants). In terms of gender distribution, the majority of participants identified as female (14), while 10 identified as male. No respondents selected non-binary or preferred not to disclose their gender.

Twelve per cent of the respondents represented organisations responsible for financing or reimbursing healthcare services. Policymakers were represented at various levels, including local (N=1), regional (N=2), national (N=2), and international (N=1). Additionally, there were respondents from health-related public authorities (N=3), healthcare regulators (N=2), and administrators (N=2). The largest group, consisting of 11 participants, fell into the "Other" category, indicating a broad range of roles beyond the predefined options.

Familiarity with AI in healthcare

The results revealed varying levels of familiarity with AI applications in healthcare, particularly in cardiovascular prevention and treatment. While five respondents considered themselves very familiar, the majority (10) reported being somewhat familiar. Additionally, four participants were slightly familiar with AI in this field, while five had no familiarity at all. Regarding organisational involvement in AI initiatives, responses were mixed. One organisation was highly supportive, while nine were moderately supportive. Three respondents maintained a neutral opinion, whereas five described their organisation as somewhat restrictive, and one considered it highly restrictive. Additionally, five participants were unsure or preferred not to answer.

Organisational involvement in AI initiatives

The survey indicates that most respondents' organisations are not directly involved in healthcare financing or reimbursement, with seventeen participants stating that their organisation does not play a role in this area, while one was unsure. Among those involved, two respondents reported that their organisation is fully responsible, namely in the role of a national health system or primary payer. Additionally, four participants indicated partial involvement, including supplementary or co-payment systems.

Regulatory perceptions and legal challenges

Regarding regulatory, legal and policy factors, the replies to the survey indicate agreement on the current state of the AI

regulations applied to cardiovascular care. While 10 respondents find current regulations moderately or highly supportive, only one sees them as highly restrictive. However, most participants view existing healthcare policies as inadequate for AI implementation, with 12 considering them somewhat or completely inadequate and only 2 seeing them as fully adequate. Additionally, nine respondents highlight the urgent need for new or adapted AI-specific regulations.

Other critical factors for AI adoption

Data privacy (N=20), patient safety (N=14), algorithm transparency (N=14), and liability (N=11) were the most selected areas of regulation that present the most significant challenges for AI adoption in healthcare. A key concern raised was the difficulty of establishing internationally applicable regulations, as harmonisation across different legal frameworks may not be feasible. Additionally, the evolving nature of AI poses regulatory challenges, as one respondent noted that in open data systems, continuously updated algorithms may change after approval, raising concerns about long-term compliance.

Other challenges mentioned included the need to improve AI literacy among stakeholders and strengthen cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive health data. The secondary use of health data for research and the sharing of information between health and social services were also identified as areas requiring clearer regulatory guidance. Additionally, the importance of integrating AI into preventive healthcare and social and health counselling was emphasised. There was also a call for innovative approaches to regulatory studies, such as assessing AI acceptability among patients and healthcare professionals, to better inform future policies.

European and international legal and regulatory initiatives

Results highlighted key lessons from AI adoption in cardiovascular healthcare, reflecting both the potential and challenges of these technologies. A recurring concern was the poor explainability of AI, which affects trust and acceptance among healthcare professionals and patients. To enhance adoption, AI tools must be "explainable, trustable, and bias-tested", ensuring transparency and reliability in clinical settings.

While some respondents acknowledged that the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the AI Act represent a strong initial step towards AI regulation, they stressed the need for further exploration of ethical considerations. One respondent specifically recommended the "8 principles of caring technology" [13] to ensure ethical AI implementation and there was also a call for innovative approaches to regulatory studies, such as assessing AI acceptability among patients and healthcare professionals, to better inform future policies.

When asked about their awareness regarding policy initiatives that facilitate AI integration in healthcare, 17 respondents were not aware of such initiatives, 6 knew a few ones and only 1 respondent knew several initiatives. In that sequence, the results identified several initiatives at both international and national levels that reflect a growing effort to support AI-driven innovation in healthcare, particularly in cardiovascular care.

At the European level, key initiatives include the "EU AI Act" [14] and the "European Health Data Space" [15], both of

which seek to create a structured and secure framework for AI use and data sharing across healthcare systems.

Additionally, global efforts such as the "World Health Organisation's Digital Health Strategy" [16] and the "OECD AI Principles" [17] provide further guidance on ethical and effective AI adoption. Other initiatives mentioned include the "AI Factories to Drive Europe's Leadership in AI" [18] and "Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) for AI" [19], which focus on fostering AI innovation and real-world application.

At the national level, several countries implement AI-focused initiatives in healthcare. In Belgium, the "Flanders AI Academy" [20] and the "Knowledge Centre Data & Society" [21] support AI research and education. The Czech Republic hosts the "National AI Days" [22] and the "Conference on the Digitisation of Czech Healthcare 2024" to promote AI integration. Germany launched the "DigiMed Bavaria Initiative" [23], focusing on cardiovascular research and the implementation of AI in cardiovascular healthcare.

In Spain, multiple initiatives were highlighted, including the "Spanish Artificial Intelligence Strategy" [24], AI applications in the "diagnosis of rare diseases", and the "Galicia 2030 Artificial Intelligence Strategic Plan" [25]. Additionally, the "European Patients' Forum" has conducted a survey on AI use in healthcare, contributing to the ongoing discussion about patient-centred AI adoption [26].

Key challenges and barriers identified

In what concerns economic factors, the survey respondents highlight economic challenges as a key factor in implementing AI in cardiovascular care. Seventeen respondents identified economic barriers as moderate (N=8), very significant (N=8), or extremely significant (N=1), while seven chose not to answer. Despite these challenges, opinions on the financial impact of AI adoption were generally positive. Ten respondents expect significant long-term savings, while another ten anticipate moderate savings. Two were unsure, and three preferred not to answer. Regarding public funding for AI research in healthcare, perceptions varied. While ten respondents reported moderate availability of funding in their region or country, only three found it to be high or very high, whereas six considered it low or very low.

When addressing technical and organisational factors, the replies to the survey indicate that technical infrastructure for AI deployment in cardiovascular care is perceived as insufficient by many respondents. Ten participants considered the availability of infrastructure to be poor, while only 5 deemed it adequate, 4 rated it as good, and 2 described it as excellent. In terms of healthcare organisations' readiness to integrate AI tools, opinions were mixed. Eight respondents believe that organisations are not very prepared to adopt AI in their workflows, while another eight considered them partially prepared. Eleven participants find very challenging to ensure interoperability and data quality for AI applications in cardiovascular care. Among them, 3 participants found it "extremely challenging," and 5 considered it "moderately challenging". Regarding healthcare data systems, 9 respondents felt that these systems either fully (5) or partially (7) support the secure and ethical use of AI in healthcare.

Referring to contextual and other barriers/enablers, the survey respondents reveal varying levels of trust in AI applications for cardiovascular care. Nine participants

reported moderate trust, while seven mentioned low trust, and five indicated high or very high public trust. Cultural and societal factors were seen as influential in AI adoption, with 13 respondents acknowledging their significant impact in their region. Regarding collaboration between sectors, 7 participants felt there was either slightly insufficient or complete insufficient collaboration to advance AI in cardiovascular care. In contrast, 6 participants believed the collaboration was either partially sufficient or fully sufficient.

The survey respondents highlighted key lessons from AI adoption in cardiovascular healthcare, reflecting both the potential and challenges of these technologies. A recurring concern is the poor explainability of AI, which affects trust and acceptance among healthcare professionals and patients.

Several key regulatory and policy changes that could support the adoption of trustworthy AI in cardiovascular healthcare were also identified, such as The EU AI Act and the GDPR. A major concern is ensuring data privacy at all phases of AI development, implementation, and monitoring, with multiple respondents stressing the need for clear protections. The approval of AI-driven healthcare solutions by national health ministries was also considered crucial, alongside the establishment of standards and guidelines for developing and validating AI algorithms.

Some respondents suggested that to accelerate AI adoption, there should be "early provisional access to evaluate acceptability and feasibility" of AI tools before full regulatory approval. Financial incentives were also mentioned, with one respondent emphasising that "to promote new measures and policies, it is necessary to offer tax incentives or subsidies for the research and development of AI solutions in cardiovascular care, promoting innovation in this field". Fostering public-private partnerships was seen as essential to "share developments, proposals, and best practices".

Another key theme was training and education, as both healthcare professionals and patients need better knowledge of AI applications to ensure informed decision-making. Regulatory changes should also focus on clarifying liability issues, with suggestions for a standardised Health Technology Assessment (HTA) process. Some participants expressed scepticism about AI regulation in their region, noting that "it is too early to speak about that", given the limited number of successful AI implementations in cardiovascular care. Others suggested bringing in fresh personnel - "new blood in the key offices" - to drive AI policy innovation.

Emerging recommendations

Data safety and privacy concerns were among the most frequently mentioned, with respondents stressing the importance of strong regulatory frameworks such as the GDPR to protect patient information.

Trust in AI was another critical factor, with multiple respondents emphasising the need for explainability, interpretability, and transparency to ensure confidence in AI-driven decisions. A major challenge is the limited availability and access to healthcare data, with some respondents advocating for the mandatory sharing of anonymous data to facilitate AI model training while preserving privacy. Additionally, the lack of local validation data and procedures was seen as a barrier to AI adoption, underscoring the need for more region-specific studies.

The integration of AI tools with electronic medical records (EMRs) and existing healthcare workflows was another recurring issue, with respondents stressing the need for seamless interoperability. Liability concerns also emerged as a major barrier, requiring clear legal frameworks to determine responsibility in AI-driven clinical decisions. Education and training were highlighted as key solutions, with calls for improved AI literacy among healthcare professionals and dedicated training programmes to support implementation.

The importance of rigorous clinical validation and regulatory approval was also emphasised, ensuring that AI tools undergo thorough testing before deployment. Respondents also pointed to ethical concerns and the need for equitable access to AI-driven healthcare. Some mentioned the risk of misalignment between AI-implemented clinical outcomes and patient goals, suggesting that AI should follow a goal-oriented care approach to better align with individual patient needs.

Other challenges included the complexity of managing multiple AI-enabled devices (such as wearables), cultural variability in remote areas (as noted in Peru), and the need to define clinical organisational structures for effective AI integration. Ultimately, respondents agreed that demonstrating clear patient benefits through real-world use cases will be key to driving broader acceptance and support for AI in healthcare.

Several insightful recommendations were proposed for policymakers and public authorities to promote the adoption of trustworthy AI in cardiovascular prevention and treatment.

A common suggestion was to "define mandatory procedures to make health data anonymously available" and to "promote data standardisation and accessibility to ensure high-quality, consistent datasets for AI training." Respondents also emphasised the need for "training to policymakers and public authorities about the benefits of AI," alongside establishing "clear regulations for the safety of AI." "Collaboration between healthcare providers, AI developers, and regulators" is seen as essential to creating "user-friendly and clinically relevant AI solutions." Additionally, respondents called for "investment in education for both the public and healthcare professionals," with a particular focus on promoting "ethical and transparent AI development by prioritising fairness, accountability, and equity."

To build trust, it was recommended to "ensure robust data privacy to safeguard patient data" and "promote pilot programs and trials" to assess the real-world impact of AI in cardiovascular care. This also involves "continuous monitoring and evaluation of AI systems," as well as advancing "health data sharing standards" and "regulation of HTA." Several respondents advocated for the establishment of "independent monitoring bodies that do quality control" and to "engage all stakeholders in setting up these regulatory bodies." This should be coupled with applying "a set of ethical principles and quality indicators" to ensure that AI in cardiovascular care remains "relevant, reliable, accessible, fair, safe, efficient, and reduces health inequity rather than increasing it."

Education efforts should also include the general public, with respondents urging to "inform and educate the general public about the possibilities and potential risks of AI" so they can make "informed choices about the use or non-use of AI applications to improve their health." Furthermore,

establishing "ethical frameworks with an emphasis on transparency, data protection, and patient consent" was identified as a crucial step to ensure the responsible deployment of AI tools. Additional recommendations included promoting "certification of AI systems for medical purposes through clinical trials and standardisation" and investing in "data infrastructure that enables the sharing of anonymised and interoperable data."

Respondents also highlighted the importance of "training healthcare staff in the use of AI tools and increasing their digital literacy" to foster trust and ensure proper implementation. Lastly, it was suggested to "create partnerships between universities, technology companies, and hospitals," and support "sandboxes (test environments) for AI experiments" under regulatory supervision. To ensure AI is accessible to a wider population, respondents called for efforts to "ensure that AI tools are also available in less developed areas and for socially disadvantaged groups," as well as reducing "the cost of implementing AI to make the solution accessible to a wide range of healthcare providers."

Additional considerations for upscaled AI implementation in healthcare included "a pilot in a country that would be useful" to test and refine AI systems before broader deployment. Additionally, the need to make information "easy to understand like a 5-year-old" was stressed to ensure accessibility. Transparency across all stakeholders was also emphasized as a crucial factor for success. Finally, there was a strong sense of urgency, with one respondent noting the "urgent need!" for timely action in this area.

Finally, respondents advocated for independent regulatory bodies to monitor and evaluate AI applications in healthcare, ensuring patient safety and adherence to ethical standards.

The results of the survey are summarised in Table 1:

Barrier	Proposed Solution
Data safety and privacy concerns	Enforce robust data protection measures aligned with the GDPR; establish independent monitoring bodies; promote patient-oriented ethical frameworks.
Lack of trust in AI	Promote explainability, transparency and interpretability of AI systems; conduct public and professional education on AI.
Limited availability and accessibility of healthcare data	Mandate the anonymised sharing of health data; invest in data infrastructure; standardise data formats to ensure consistency.
Absence of local validation and clinical relevance	Conduct region-specific studies and clinical trials; encourage certification of AI systems through validated protocols.
Integration challenges with existing systems (e.g., EMRs)	Develop interoperable solutions; promote collaboration between AI developers and healthcare providers to ensure seamless integration.
Legal liability and accountability	Establish clear legal frameworks defining responsibility in AI-assisted clinical decisions and involve regulators.
Lack of education and training among HCPs	Introduce dedicated AI training programmes and improve digital literacy; invest in continuous professional development.

Barrier	Proposed Solution
Ethical concerns and equity issues	Apply ethical principles; ensure equitable access to AI tools, particularly for underserved populations.
Misalignment between outputs and patient goals	Promote goal-oriented AI development aligned with individual patient needs; integrate patient perspectives in AI design.
Complexity of multiple AI-enabled devices	Design user-friendly systems and define clinical organisational structures to support coordinated use.
Cultural and regional variability	Tailor AI applications to local contexts; engage local stakeholders, especially in remote or under-resourced regions.
High costs and unequal access	Invest in low-cost solutions; promote accessibility for socially disadvantaged and low-resource healthcare settings.
Lack of RWE and evidence based benefits	Launch pilot programmes; evaluate AI applications through real-world use cases to demonstrate tangible patient outcomes.
Inadequate policymaker engagement and understanding	Provide training for policymakers; promote collaboration across sectors (academia, tech industry, healthcare, regulators).
Need for overarching regulatory and ethical oversight	Establish independent regulatory bodies; implement continuous monitoring and evaluation frameworks; define and apply quality indicators.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Data quality and interoperability emerged as critical factors influencing the successful deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) in cardiovascular healthcare. Respondents consistently highlighted the importance of ensuring high data quality prior to the training of AI and machine learning models. Additionally, enhancing interoperability services was identified as essential to facilitate seamless integration with

The delicate balance between the protection of privacy and the need for data is a topic that should be included in future research and stakeholder discussions.

Despite the mentioned regulatory and technical challenges, AI was generally viewed as offering substantial potential in the cardiovascular domain. Survey participants noted that AI technologies could enhance diagnostic capabilities, support personalised care pathways, and enable more informed clinical decision-making. Specific benefits already being observed include improved allocation of healthcare resources, more accurate prediction of adverse events, and the development of personalised treatment algorithms.

The existence of reimbursement pathways for certain AI applications further underlines their growing role in cardiovascular prevention and treatment. However, financial constraints remain a concern. The high costs associated with testing and assessment of AI solutions were acknowledged, although some participants noted that long-term healthcare costs may be reduced following successful implementation.

Divergent perspectives were also expressed regarding Health Technology Assessment (HTA). While some views characterised existing HTA processes as outdated, others emphasised the importance of transparent evaluation prior to widespread adoption, even if this introduces delays. Stakeholder collaboration was identified as a key enabler for effective AI integration. Engagement from healthcare professionals, patients, and policymakers was considered key for ensuring that AI systems are both clinically relevant and ethically deployed. Moreover, there is a recognised need for personalised training programmes aimed at equipping healthcare professionals and patients with the skills necessary to navigate AI-supported care environments.

Looking forward, AI is expected to play an essential role in advancing integrated care models. Its potential to enhance person-centred, coordinated, and continuous care was widely acknowledged. Nevertheless, ensuring clear accountability, minimising the risk of AI-related errors, and promoting ongoing innovation were seen as essential prerequisites for the sustainable and ethical adoption of AI in cardiovascular prevention and treatment.

Our findings highlight both the promise and complexity of AI adoption in cardiology. Overcoming regulatory, ethical, and technical challenges will require strong stakeholder collaboration, improved AI literacy, and adaptive regulatory frameworks to foster trust and ensure sustainable implementation. These insights extend beyond cardiology, offering valuable guidance for AI adoption in other healthcare domains where similar challenges are equally critical.

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